

About the locution 'lunar standstill' and the term 'lunistic'

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna
Politecnico di Torino

Today, in the English literature concerning archaeoastronomy, we find used the locution 'lunar standstill', which was apparently introduced by Alexander Thom in 1971, in his book *Megalithic Lunar Observatories*. However a term already existed to describe the same astronomical phenomenon: it was 'lunistic', proposed by Joseph De la Lande in the eighteenth century.

Written in Turin, 23 December 2018. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2525323

The moon has an apparent motion in the sky, which is more complex than that of the sun. We know that the sunrise - or sunset - direction oscillates between the two solstice positions during a year; the moon does the same during a nodal period (about 27 days). Moreover, the moon has a period – the lunar standstill period (about 18.6 years) – on which the values of the extremal directions (standstills) are changing. In this manner there are major and minor standstills, of which we can calculate moonrise/moonset directions. These directions are depending on latitude. For a latitude of about 45° , like that of Torino for instance, we have that the minor and major northernmost moonrise azimuths (directions) are 47.40° and 65.65° (angles are given from true north). The minor and major southernmost moonrise azimuths are 116.35° and 132.58° . The azimuths of sunrise on summer and winter solstices are between these lunar azimuths.

The locution "lunar standstill" was apparently first used in 1971, by Alexander Thom in his book *Megalithic Lunar Observatories* [1]. For the sun, the equivalent locution could be "solar standstill", to describe the term "solstice", which derives from the Latin *solstitium*. "Solstice" describes the extremes in the Sun's varying declination. As explained in [1], neither the Sun nor the Moon stands still, obviously; what stops, momentarily, is the change in declination.

After the book written by Thom, the locution "lunar standstill" is quite used by the English literature, in books and articles focussed on archaeoastronomical studies. However, a term already existed to describe the lunar standstill; it is 'lunistic'. It is possible to find it in English books, such as in [2]. In this reference we find a very interesting discussion, concerning the moon influencing the weather. This influence has, "in all ages, been believed by the generality of mankind: the same opinion was embraced by the ancient philosophers; and several eminent philosophers of later times have thought the opinion not unworthy of notice". It is also told that "Although the moon only acts (as far at least as we can ascertain) on the waters of the ocean by producing tides, it is nevertheless highly probable, according to the observations of Lambert, Toaldo, and Cotte, that in consequence of the lunar influence, great variations do take place in the atmosphere, and consequently in the weather" [2].

However, who was the first that used the term "lunistic"?

In [2]: "There are ten situations in the moon's orbit when she must particularly exert her influence on the atmosphere; and when, consequently, changes of the weather most readily take place. These are: 1st the new, and 2d, the full moon, when she exerts her influence in conjunction with, or in opposition, to the sun. 3d and 4th, the quadratures, or those aspects of the moon when she is 90°

distant from the sun; or when she is in the middle point of her orbit, between the points of conjunction and opposition, namely, in the first and third quarters. 5th, the perigee, and 6th, the apogee, or those points of the moon's orbit, in which she is at the least and greatest distance from the earth. 7th and 8th, the two passages of the moon over the equator, one of which Toaldo calls the moon's ascending, and the other the moon's descending, equinox; or the two *lunistices, as De la Lande terms them*. 9th, The boreal lunistice, when the moon approaches as near as she can in each lunation (or period between one new moon and another) to our zenith (that point in the horizon which is directly over our heads). 10th, The austral lunistice, when she is at the greatest distance from our zenith, for the action of the moon varies greatly according to her obliquity.”

So, De la Lande was the first to use the term “lunistice”. Also in [3], it is told the same.

Let us remember two references to the De la Lande ‘s works in [4].

Joseph Jérôme Lefrançois De la Lande, (Bourg-en-Bresse, 11 July 1732 - Paris, 4 April 1807) was a French astronomer [5]. Director of the Paris Observatory, from 1795 to 1801 he compiled the most complete list of his time, with the indications of the position of 47.390 stars (Histoire Céleste Française). Together with the British scientist John Flamsteed, De la Lande was the first to list the brightest stars (French edition of 1645-1719). A star that he put in his list bears his name today: it is the star La Lande 21185. Born in Bourg, in the French department of Ain, his parents sent him to study as a lawyer in Paris. However, he attended also the Hôtel Cluny, where Joseph Nicolas Delisle had his observatory, becoming fond of astronomy. He thus became a pupil of Delisle and Pierre Lemonnier. After completing his studies, De la Lande returned to Bourg to be a lawyer. The turning point of his existence happened when Lemonnier proposed him to go to Berlin, for measurements of the lunar parallax, which was started at Cape of Good Hope, by Nicolas Louis De la Caille [6]. It was in 1751-52. De la Lande and De la Caille (1713-1762) used a triangulation method to determine the distance of the moon from the earth [7].

Concerning the ten situations of the moon, in [2] we find also mentioned Toaldo. Giuseppe Toaldo was an Abbot and a Professor of Astrology. In [8], it is told that in 1761 the Venetian Senate decided to instate an Observatory for the University of Padua, in the ancient Torlonga of the Carraresi Castle. Thanks to Toaldo and the architect Domenico Cerato, the Specola was completed in 1777, becoming one of the most important observatories in Europe. This observatory is mentioned by Goethe in his "Italian Journey".

For what concerns the observations of the lunistics - boreal and austral lunistics -, they were well known by ancient people and considered as very important. This is shown by the many ancient monuments oriented along the directions of moonrise and moonset on lunar standstill. Examples of astronomical orientations according to moonrise and moonset on lunistics were given by author in some recent articles (see for instance [9-15]).

References

[1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lunar_standstill#Origin_of_name

[2] An Encyclopaedia of Gardening, Comprising the Theory and Practice of Horticulture, Floriculture, Arboriculture and Landscape-gardening, Including... a General History of Gardening in All Countries. John Claudius Loudon. Printed for Longman, Hurst, Rees, Orme, Brown, and Green.1824.

[3] Completa raccolta di opuscoli, osservazioni, e notizie diverse contenute nei giornali astro-meteorologici, dall'anno 1773 sino all'anno 1798 del fu signo abate Giuseppe Toaldo. Tomo primo, Venezia. 1802. Al link <https://archive.org/details/completaraccolt00metgoog/page/n24>

[4] Astronomie, par M. de La Lande ... Tome premier (-quatrieme), Volume 4, chez la Veuve Desaint, rue du Foin Saint Jacques, 1781. Traité du flux et du reflux de la mer Joseph Jérôme Le François de Lalande. 1781

[5] www.bolognart.com/joomla/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=111%3Ade-la-lande-biografia&catid=45%3Acartografi-biografie&Itemid=37

[6] Sparavigna, A. C. (2012). Two amateur astronomers at Berkeley. arXiv preprint arXiv:1202.0950.

- [7] <http://www.eso.org/public/outreach/eduoff/aol/market/experiments/advanced/skills301.html>
- [8] <https://www.watermuseumofvenice.com/network-en/the-specola-tower-en/>
- [9] Sparavigna, A. C. (2107). Alignment Along the Moonrise on Major Lunar Standstills of the Pipers, the Pair of Standing Stones at St Buryan. PHILICA Article number 1127, 2017. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3053524>
- [10] Sparavigna, A. C. (2016). The Temple Complex of Ggantija and the Major Lunar Standstill as Given by the Photographer's Ephemeris. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2828614> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2828614>
- [11] Sparavigna, A. C. (2016). Megalithic Quadrangles and the Ancient Astronomy. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2862330> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2862330>
- [12] Sparavigna, A. C. (2016). Astronomical Alignments of Ales Stenar Along Sunset and Moonset Directions. PHILICA Article 663. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2818991>
- [13] Sparavigna, A. C. (2017). Astronomical Orientations of the Great Enclosure of Musawwarat Es Sufra. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2918176> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2918176>
- [14] Sparavigna, A. C. (2018). The Bent Pyramid and the Major Lunar Standstill. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3143050> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3143050>
- [15] Sparavigna, A. C. (2018). Lilybaeum (Marsala) and the Major Lunar Standstill. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2316067>